

Vers une modélisation pratique des liens entre l'intelligence territoriale et les destinations touristiques

Towards a practical modeling of the links between the territorial intelligence and tourist destinations

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Résumé

La définition, l'évolution et les aspects importants du concept d'intelligence territoriale (IT) sont présentés dans cet ouvrage. En conséquence, les outils créés pour TI sont affichés en tenant compte de l'emplacement, du thème et des outils. Les situations où les deux idées ont été mises en œuvre se sont révélées significatives pour l'objectif de cette recherche, qui consiste à relier TI et tourisme. La quête du tourisme pour des expériences uniques nécessite de valoriser les communautés d'accueil, ce qui est rendu possible grâce à TI. Un modèle conceptuel liant Intelligence Territoriale et Destinations Touristiques a été mis en place. L'objectif est donc de mettre en évidence le lien entre les différentes variables de l'étude en abordant une étude exploratoire. Ensuite, une étude confirmatoire pour tester les hypothèses de recherche.

Mots clés :

Intelligence territoriale ; développement durable; gouvernance; TIC; modèle conceptuel.

Abstract

The definition, evolution, and important aspects of the territorial intelligence (TI) concept are presented in this work. As a result, the tools created for TI are displayed, taking into consideration the location, theme and tools. The situations where both ideas have been implemented are shown to be significant for the goal of this research, which is about connecting TI and tourism. Tourism's quest for unique experiences necessitates valuing host communities, which is made possible through TI. A conceptual model linking Territorial Intelligence and Tourist Destinations was implemented. The objective is therefore to highlight the link between the different variables of the study by approaching an exploratory study. Then, a confirmatory study to test the research hypotheses.

Keywords

Territorial intelligence; sustainable development; governance; TIC; conceptual model.

Introduction

Some of the problems that society is currently experiencing are due to the prevailing economic model, based on consumption, where unlimited growth is the maxim that cannibalizes natural and cultural resources, and leads to increasingly pronounced social inequalities. A society that seeks to resolve these differences through not only economic but also comprehensive measures must act intelligently given the degree of existing knowledge. It is in this context that the concept of "territorial intelligence" arises, with the three elements that define it: "sustainable development", "governance" and "New Information and Communication Technologies".

In another order of things, one of the activities of greatest global importance is tourism, which is defined under rules of consumption of leisure time, and where the commodification of resources, standardization and homogenization have marked its evolution over time.

Today, there are new ways of doing tourism, where the authentic and the search for experiences prevail, which is why heritage, culture, local identity have become fundamental aspects on which destination managers attract tourists.

Tourism is a sector that develops in a specific territory, which is capable of generating experiences through its material and immaterial resources, and where there is a great diversity of actors involved; therefore, a priori it could be a participant in its own initiatives of territorial intelligence.

With these two elements as a base –territorial intelligence and tourism– the basic objective of this paper is to make a first approximation between the aforementioned link, attending to conceptual aspects, analyzing applications-projects developed and investigating the points of connection between both terms. For this, the paper begins by defining the concept and evolution of the term territorial intelligence, continues by explaining the key elements, to conclude, with concrete examples that link territorial intelligence and the tourism. Finally, by way of reflection, some lines of future research are proposed that may be useful in advancing these novel approaches within the framework of the tourist use of the territories. It is necessary to state that today there are very few jobs where territorial intelligence and tourism are linked, while in other fields of action, such as employment, territorial planning, social integration or poverty, they are more abundant. It is for this reason that this paper tries to provide the state of the matter, in order to be able to advance in the link between territorial intelligence and tourism.

1. CONCEPTION AND EVOLUTION OF THE TERM TERRITORIAL INTELLIGENCE

The concept and the tools of territorial intelligence have their origin in the late eighties, to respond to the needs of a group of territorial actors who worked on projects to combat poverty (Miedes, 2008). In 1989, the absence of territorial plans based on participation, the demand for critical approaches in the field of sustainable development, and the revolution in information and communication technologies (ICTs), gave rise to the emergence in Europe (Besançon, France) the "Catalyse" method (Perea-Medina et al., 2018), whose main objective was the creation of collective intelligence through various tools (diagnosis and evaluation), so that the actors could elaborate, argue, encourage and evaluate sustainable development projects. From France and from 1994, this project was extended to Spain, Belgium, Romania and Hungary. The first definition of Territorial Intelligence to be proposed is "a means for researchers, for actors and for the territorial community to acquire a better knowledge of the territory, but also to better control its development (...)" (Perea-Medina et al., 2018). Our research already includes the two fundamental aspects that will mark other definitions: the scientific approach and the actors-territorial community (Bertacchini, 2004; Devillet & Breuer, 2009; Maza, 2010; Perea-Medina et al., 2018; Silvera et al., 2012). The scientific approach in territorial intelligence has the function of integrating and developing the multidisciplinary knowledge and the necessary methods to understand the territorial structures, the territorial systems and the dynamics of the territories (Soulie et al., 2011). It follows that territorial intelligence cannot be seen as a discipline, it is not the simple sum of knowledge, but is made up of a set of knowledge obtained through observation and structured reasoning.

The actors-territorial community represent the second pillar of territorial intelligence, in fact it is defined as a process that is based on the understanding that articulates knowledge, co-participation, co-construction and collaboration being essential. by the different actors (Bozzano et al., 2010; Karol et al., 2011; Masselot, 2009). With these three items, work can be done to generate the comprehensive development of the areas with the greatest difficulties, which translates into a better articulation and combination of the economic, social and environmental objectives of a territory. In fact, Bozzano argues that a territory can never be intelligent without the presence of the actors who are ones who imprint said quality on it (Bozzano et al., 2010). So that, we speak of territorial intelligence when the actors – managers or not – know the territory well or make an effort to know it through access to information of all kinds, as long as said knowledge is used, and this is important to remember, in a territorially sustainable way. .

Together with the scientific approach and the actors, the tools become key parts of this entire process, fundamentally because the current information society has scientific methods and tools that, through ICTs, can reach the actors who want it. and facilitate the search for alternatives to wasting resources. In fact, in the above definition it is recognized that“(...) the appropriation of communication and information technologies, in itself, is an essential stage for the actors to introduce a learning process that will allow them to act in a pertinent and efficient manner (...)” (Girardot, 2010: 15). That is why the concept of "information" must be understood from the point of view of exchange, mutualization, organization and knowledge, in order to facilitate the collaborative work of the actors involved in a territory (BERTACCHINI, 2004; Devillet & Breuer, 2009). And the concept of "communication" must act first, as the guiding thread of the information“(...) culture, information, identity, transmission and heritage are of great importance (...) from information and communication sciences, in the Data-Information- Action process (...) information is structured and managed , co-building knowledge and communications (...)”(Bozzano, 2013); and second, as a “pooling” that arises when communities communicate and mediate on a cultural, exchange and needs level. In this sense, it refers to collective learning, where the actors think and live their "what for" and territorial intelligence provides them with the tool to solve the "how". Therefore, education, the transmission of knowledge and the culture of local actors, is essential for the construction of ICTs and to understand the need for social intervention.

A current and interesting debate is whether territorial intelligence is a science or not. The definition used by the European Network of Territorial Intelligence (ENTI) cites that the“Territorial Intelligence is the science whose objective is sustainable development and whose subject is the territorial community”(Girardot, 2009). However, the same author has an evolution in this regard, because initially he states that it is a "means" for researchers, later he refers to a "multidisciplinary knowledge" to, finally, speak of science. But he is not the only one who raises such controversy, Frediani (2012) also proposes that territorial intelligence is a way of doing science. However, authors such as Girardot (2000), Devillet (2008)⁷, Masselot (2013) and Sánchez (2013) who propose that territorial intelligence is a scientific approach due to its multidisciplinary nature, it is not considered as a science. Coinciding with this idea, the researchers of this communication position themselves in the debate with the view that territorial intelligence is understood as a scientific approach. Therefore, the definition given by Devillet (Bozzano, 2013: 5) could be taken as the most representative reference: “Territorial intelligence is a collective scientific approach to mobilizing intelligence within a region... in order to improve individual well-being and increase the resilience of the territory within the framework of sustainable development. It is a

transversal approach that involves the consideration of all sectors of activity and the mobilization of the actors of the territory and interdisciplinary institutional researchers...". What the research does agree on is the relevance given to social and environmental development. Thus, one might think that the economic dimension is already implicit, if one takes into account that territorial intelligence tries to make resources available to the actors. But it can be argued that an approach where the economic aspect does not prevail a priori is complex to apply, given that the primacy of consumerism, one of the basic pillars of capitalism, goes against these territories. This is justified in the evolution of the concept of territorial intelligence, where from the beginning an attempt has been made to link it to a concept of economic origin, but which may not correspond to the reality of the concept of territorial intelligence.

It is argued that "collective intelligence" (CI) and "economic intelligence" (EI) can be considered conceptual referents of territorial intelligence. The idea of "territorial knowledge management" (GCT) was derived from the CI, which deals with actions that seek human development and the constant improvement of the quality of life of citizens (Alfaro, 2002). In turn, the EI drifted towards the idea of "territorial economic intelligence" (IET), understood as the creation of products and services through economic intelligence for the economic innovation of the actors and (...) the development of digital territories (Goria, 2006).

However, and according to Girardot (2008), these definitions derived from EI differ from the one given for territorial intelligence. Therefore, TI should not be confused with EIT because, although it is true that both use information and communication technologies as tools, they differ in terms of their objectives. Territorial intelligence does not perceive the territory as a market, but as a participatory and collaborative space, but this is already raised by the CI when it is defined as "the results of collaboration and information exchange, as well as competition between individuals which can be considered a form of network, which has been made possible by recent developments in information technology" (Girardot, 2010: 29). However, in the IET the actors and the territory are at the "service" of economic intelligence, and not the other way around, as defined by territorial intelligence, where the actors use the territory for their well-being and development.

2. FUNDAMENTALS, TOOLS AND APPLICATIONS OF TERRITORIAL INTELLIGENCE

2.1. The basics of territorial intelligence

Knowing the definition and origin of territorial intelligence, it is necessary to advance in its foundations from the approach to its three main elements: sustainable development, governance and new information and communication technologies.

2.1.1. Sustainable development

Sustainable development, understood as a vision of the future that is capable of dealing with environmental problems and the unequal distribution of resources, contains three dimensions: human needs, the limitations of the global ecosystem and greater economic development. That is why the concept is linked to the need for a human-territory relationship that allows the conservation of the environment so that it continues to be productive. What we call sustainability is, therefore, the result of a pattern of organization (De Franco, 2000). It is understood that sustainable development is related to quality of life and should not be confused with economic growth alone. What is contradictory is that as concern for sustainability grows, the unsustainability of an economic model dominated by industrial civilization (Naredo, 1997) implicitly arises, which favors the countries of the so-called first world, to increasingly impoverish to countries with fewer possibilities but with more resources, which are exploited by the so-called "developed countries". However, the sustainable development model, fundamentally due to the ambiguity of the concept, has led to its use more as a "theoretical magic formula" than as a real application that proposes solutions on the territory, in fact, various authors such as Naredo (1997) they state that under the umbrella of sustainable development (Naredo, 1997), purely economic actions have simply been developed, using the environment and society as an excuse. It is for these reasons that territorial intelligence is proposed as action-research. The fact that human communities are the main focus for territorial intelligence is explained by the real importance that has been given to sustainable development from a local point of view. It is more feasible to achieve sustainable development at the local level, where the actors are in direct contact with their territory. It is intended to strengthen local capacities and initiatives, proximity to problems, needs and resources, as well as allowing citizens to develop actions and strategies for development. To implement these participatory models based on micro-problems, micro-actions and micro-transformations, it is necessary to take into account the scale factor.

2.1.2. Governance

The concept of governance has been profusely addressed in the last two decades. In principle, there is a clear differentiation between the idea of government and governance since, while the government is characterized by the presence of a power (State) organized through public powers with hierarchical relationships, governance refers to the birth of a new system more complex relational, which includes actors outside politics, representing an alternative to the public management model (Farinós, 2008). Taking into account the bases of territorial intelligence, governance must have a network-based approach (Messner et al., 1994; Pierre, 2000; Peters, 2006) and a socio-centric system: the focus of attention is coordination, self-government and decentralization. At the same time, It is necessary that hierarchical differences be minimized and that a horizontal structure be followed, where agreements and decisions are the result of a consensus between the actors involved (Salcido & Ramos Chávez, 2008). The “public” must include the institutions and the society, that is, a multilevel governance and active participation of the population. For this, transfer and coordination relationships are required (Almansa, 2010). One of the keys to success is having a scientific basis in the tools that accompany the action procedures, to ensure the effectiveness of multilevel governance. One of the most used tools are the "territorial observatories", which must be able to obtain data and capitalize on the knowledge generated through ICT, in order to develop planning, management and evaluation processes, according to the bases of governance. . But the reality is less hopeful, because the idea of governance does not prevail in the majority of rulers who usually have a short-term vision and are very biased in relation to their field of interest. For a territory to be smart and have a good governance system, a culture of cooperation is necessary not only at the local level, but also at the regional, national and global levels. Where politicians, businessmen and citizens have similar approaches on long-term economic, social and environmental sustainability, far from their years of candidacy or business benefits at the cost of everything. It is presented as an arduous task, since in a globalized and capitalist economy, one does not usually see beyond economic aspirations and individual benefits.

2.1.3. TIC

Territorial intelligence should configure and develop socio-technical systems to make effective social integration with the territory. For this, the actors require communication tools and techniques, but they must be able to make them evolve by expressing the needs that arise with their use. In this sense, the first requirement that territorial intelligence considers is to promote

the dissemination of information, in a communication environment that is capable of transferring the local to the global, and that serves to know the needs of a population in order to Act. From the information and communication sciences, the "informational" and anthropological process supposes the conjunction of three hypotheses (Bertacchini, 2000): (1) the actors exchange information (energy generation at the individual or collective level); (2) the actors give credibility to the information they receive (capture and exchange of information); (3) once the information process has been established, the actors develop the appropriate networks and transfer their skills and knowledge (mobilization and transfer of energy: formulation of a development project). The union of these three hypotheses means that the skills and knowledge of the actors can be identified through the information they have transmitted and can be transferred to the rest of the community, thus the information collected can be transformed into local development actions. (3) once the information process has been established, the actors develop the appropriate networks and transfer their skills and knowledge (mobilization and transfer of energy: formulation of a development project). The union of these three hypotheses means that the skills and knowledge of the actors can be identified through the information they have transmitted and can be transferred to the rest of the community, thus the information collected can be transformed into local development actions. (3) once the information process has been established, the actors develop the appropriate networks and transfer their skills and knowledge (mobilization and transfer of energy: formulation of a development project). The union of these three hypotheses means that the skills and knowledge of the actors can be identified through the information they have transmitted and can be transferred to the rest of the community, thus the information collected can be transformed into local development actions. In order for ICTs to provide tools for territorial intelligence, the following requirements must be met (Girardot, 2010): (1) methods and tools understandable by the actors and respectful of the ethics of sustainable development; (2) disseminate the fundamental methods of analysis of the territories (Territorial Information System) and the processing of territorial data; (3) promote application of the principles of governance, knowledge sharing and facilitating territorial research-action. The function of ICT for the implementation of territorial intelligence processes is basic, since it concerns the analysis of scientific methods, generic tools such as Software and GIS, the development of a systemic vision of the concept of territory, an approach of territorial information and the implementation of the principles of collaboration and participation. But this scenario dominated by ICT generates other conflicts and inequalities since these tools should have served to promote

territorial equality and equity, however, on many occasions they have served to increase differences and promote the decline of regions, those that they do not have the resources to access them (Calderón et al., 2012). It is for this reason that territorial intelligence proposes the design of adaptive tools for the territories, taking into account their technological difficulties and their limitations. ICTs that contribute to development, that solve problems and cover needs, and that serve as a means to reduce existing cultural, economic and social inequalities (United Nations, 2005).

3. TERRITORIAL INTELLIGENCE AND TOURISM: SOME APPLICATIONS

As has been indicated, the topics addressed with methodologies specific to territorial intelligence are varied and disparate, for example, in the case of Europe, actions have been carried out in the field of immigration, social problems in disadvantaged regions, employment, etc., while in Latin America, the fields of action have been agriculture, territorial planning, tourism, social integration and poverty. Tourism projects have been scarce, in fact only some actions have been found that combine territorial intelligence and tourism: (1) Uruguay (Punta del Este) in 2009, where work was done to generate employment, promoting ecological innovation and social, as well as the enhancement of the natural and cultural resources of the destination; (2) Uruguay (Lavalleja) in 2010, in which tourism was treated in order to conserve biodiversity and cultural heritage, and investigating how it affects the quality of life of the population; (3) Argentina (La Plata) in 2012, it is about rescuing the heritage assets that are linked to the city and its social practices; (4) Argentina (Brandsen) in 2012, the "La Posada Ecological Parador" is carried out to revalue the cultural and natural heritage and generate links with local actors; (5) Argentina (Santa Fé and Paraná) in 2011, the project "Organization of Territorial Intelligence, for Sustainable Tourism of the RMSP" was carried out. Of this series of territorial intelligence initiatives focused on tourism, the last two have been analyzed in detail, which, like the rest, try to be promoted and developed from the host communities themselves (Gliemmo, 2012: 1). The way of doing tourism is changing, more and more experiences and emotions are sought, that is, the individual is sought, hence it is essential that tourism seeks an appreciation of local identities, but not only as a "myth", but as a reality, where standardization and homogenization do not affect its culture. Society is the one that creates the essence of a place, the one that lives in the territory and the one that hosts it, any transformation that does not take local actors into account will not make sense.

3.1. Posada Ecological Parador project

The project of this environmental and social center is carried out in the municipality of Brandsen in the Province of Buenos Aires, rural area (23 inhabitants/km²) on the route that connects the Metropolitan Area of Buenos Aires and the tourist corridor of the Atlantic Coast of Buenos Aires (where La Plata is located, one of the most important tourist destinations within the sun and beach segment of the country). The intervention proposal stems from a problem, the location of new urbanizations in rural areas motivated by the proximity to La Plata, which has caused a serious social polarization, with little social and territorial integration of these new residential areas with high purchasing power, and has caused serious environmental impacts due to the proliferation of clandestine dumps that affect the quality of life of the local population. Thus, the project proposes a center for the environmental recovery of one of the areas degraded by the execution of Highway that connects Buenos Aires with Mar del Plata. The important thing about this action is not only the objective it pursues, but also the participatory method and how the information (environmental, social and economic) helped to define the needs. The environmental-cultural study, the conducting of surveys of the local population and the participatory workshops stand out, the project was agreed upon in each of its stages. In short, it is about planning from the bottom up, in addition to establishing criteria for natural, cultural and social preservation. This reconversion of a degraded space not only remedy the environmental-urban situation that generates socioeconomic conflicts, but it has also created a space capable of generating appropriation by the local population, where they identify and share with visitors.

3.2. Organization of Territorial Intelligence, for the Sustainable Tourism

This initiative is organized around the cities of Santa Fe and Paraná (Province of Entre Ríos in Argentina). The idea arises after detecting a problematic social context, where economic growth processes that increase social inequalities, low degrees of public-private cooperation, poor training, decreased quality of life due to the loss of value of natural resources and also the cultural ones. Based on a participatory diagnosis, two objectives were established: the creation of an Urban Environment Biosphere Reserve for both cities, through collaboration with international organizations, academic and political actors; and, secondly, the creation of the "Organization of Territorial Intelligence, for Sustainable Tourism", integrating institutional organizations in matters political, scientific, technological and training, business associations and citizenship. Tourism was considered as a key element given the growth in both cities with

three actions: (1) tourist strategies, programs and projects where sustainability was the reference, (2) a cooperation network was created with representation of all the actors, (3) and the creation of a Regional Center for Territorial Intelligence for Sustainable Development was planned, as an observatory. In conclusion, both cases differ due to the nature of the projects, the type of space, the degree of tourism development, etc. However, the key to both is the method and objectives for conflict resolution. They begin with co-construction in its first diagnosis stage, where the problems are also transmitted by the actors, and co-participation continues to propose improvement actions; it is the transformation from the bottom up, delving into people and their involvement, which entails an appropriation of the initiatives by taking them as their own. It is now that what Bozzano (2011) identifies as the triple simultaneous objective that territorial intelligence must contribute to tourism is understood: subjects, projects and territories, and it is necessary to work for identities, needs and expectations.

4. Conceptual model of Territorial Intelligence

Based on the above studies, Figure 1 presents the conceptual model of Territorial Intelligence implemented in AMOS SPSS 22.

Fig.1 Conceptual model of Territorial Intelligence

Source: Author

The empirical study will present our conceptual model, the epistemological positioning of the research, as well as the methodology adopted. We will discuss the choice of the type of research (quantitative), the choice of tools adopted (administered questionnaire), the choice of our samples as well as the methods of analysis (quantitative structural equation model).

The objective of our research is therefore to highlight the link between the different variables of the study. To do this, we first approach an exploratory study. Then, a confirmatory study will be carried out to test the research hypotheses.

In fact, the validation of measurement scales is done in two phases (Gerbing and Anderson, 1988):

- a phase of Exploratory Factorial Analysis (EFA) allowing to purify the scales and to evaluate their dimensionality;
- a Confirmatory Factorial Analysis (CFA) phase, to assess the reliability and validity of the instrument. This phase is able to decide on the dimensionality of the scale when the exploratory phase does not allow it.

We will study in future works the procedure of the two analysis methods used, namely the analysis of main components for the experimental phase and the method of structural equations on a measurement model for the confirmatory factual analysis.

Conclusion

In this paper, we studied three research groups (Regional Geographic Analysis, Tourism and Territory, Group of Cooperative Information Systems) work in an integrated manner on the processes that link tourist activity, territories and the concept of “intelligence”. It is expected that in the coming years, the relationship between territorial intelligence and tourism will be a topic of great interest, either from the new concept of "Intelligent Tourist Destinations" (DTI), or from Territorial Intelligence applied to Tourist Destinations. Along these lines, there has been a commitment to a reading of the "intelligence" processes applied to tourist territories focused on governance and work with the actors, rather than on a solely and exclusively technological approach, which is the one for which they are betting on the new "intelligent tourist destinations" forgetting, in most cases, the actors of the territory, true orchestrators in any process of change and improvement. It is about technologies being the guiding threads of information and knowledge, but they are not the end of actions. This is where the turning point arises, in the use of ICTs, since it is this nuance that underlies the main difference between "Smart Tourist Destinations" and "Territorial Intelligence applied to Tourist Destinations". At this time, where the valorization of different spaces by tourism tends to reproduce attractions, often disconnected from their history and identities, from their environmental characteristics and disjointed from other economic activities, it is argued that territorial intelligence provides a theoretical- robust and contrasted methodology. Territorial Intelligence can be applied to any tourist destination, whatever the degree of maturity, the tourist segment, etc., helping to improve the planning and management processes of tourism and the destination.

It would provide a more holistic and consensual vision that would have a positive impact on all the actors involved. To do this, destination planners and managers must anticipate and adapt to the new needs of tourism, and the concept and tools of territorial intelligence can help the new emerging paradigm of the tourism sector. In this new paradigm, tourists are increasingly mobilized in search of sociocultural diversity, of new practices that evoke experience, the return of the individual and the rupture of daily life; at the same time, it requires greater preservation of the environment –in its broadest sense–, it refers to maintaining the values of a society and its identity, which is not a territory “theatricalized” by tourism, It should be argued that territorial intelligence is capable of covering the problems exposed in this research –territorial and social delimitation, sustainability and governance–, being able to present itself as a new alternative to traditional tourism planning and management models. Where the participation of all the actors is vital to plan and manage, since through the tools provided by territorial

intelligence it is possible to carry out this active participation. However, the main difficulty that arises in adapting the theoretical-methodological framework of territorial intelligence to any tourist destination is scale. Until today, the interventions that have been carried out have been on a micro-scale, and a tourist destination, as a general rule, is a broader and more complex territory. One way to solve this problem would be through interventions in the different "districts" (Dredge, 1999) that make up the tourist destination, given that the sum of the different "districts" gives rise to "counties" that make up the destination. The example of the study area has not been random, this state of the question and the problems of scales are the beginning of a line of future research, where it is proposed to use the tools of territorial intelligence in the management and planning processes of tourist destinations, taking as an area of intervention and experimentation. The purpose of this line of research is to determine to what extent and in what way tourist practices affect the co-construction of a tourist territory, understood from the identity, need and expectations of local actors. In short, proposing territorial intelligence actions in tourist destinations hand in hand with research-action can be positive, if progress is made in governance, understood as transparent and participatory good governance, and in sustainability, if tourism serves to improve the "state of justice" as proposed by the philosopher Adela Cortina.

In conclusion, if territorial intelligence only advances in technology, despite the positive results of greater energy efficiency and more sustainable mobility, the advances "intelligent" will be very biased; paraphrasing the architect and philosopher Eduardo Prieto (2014) "The city is the problem; the technique, the solution", is the territory the problem? Is the destination the problem? Apparently not, hence the relationship between territorial intelligence and tourist destinations is a line of present and future research of enormous interest based on the conceptual model of Territorial Intelligence implemented in this study.

Future scope

In future works, we will conduct a survey to test the causal structure of the research model, by characterizing the hypotheses that relate to the causal relationships between the different variables of our model. This second phase of our study will be carried out by administering a questionnaire which relates to the variables of our model, and which can be adopted from the literature and studies already published.

To analyze the results of this second phase, it will be necessary to validate the measurement scales on the one hand, and to validate the hypotheses on the other. So before testing the hypotheses, it is necessary to measure the different concepts.

We will try to show later that the measurement scales will be validated by following two phases (Gerbing and Anderson, 1988): an Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) phase allowing the scales to be refined and their dimensionality to be evaluated, and a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) phase, enabling the reliability and validity of the instrument to be assessed. While to test the research hypotheses, we will use structural equation modeling.

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